

A SCALABLE, MORE EXTENSIBLE ARCHITECTURE FOR ABAQUS

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AUTHOR(S):

Ahmed Darwish

SUPERVISOR(S):

Michele Grossi

Sofia Vallecoras

Alberto Di Meglio

PROJECT SPECIFICATION

The main high-level goal of this project was to modify the existing architecture of the initial ABAQUS proof-of-concept prototype, such that it is more extensible by the community and easily integrable into existing software stacks and systems.

Initial discussions resulted in the final decision that the platform shall follow a scheduler architecture, where interaction with the platform mainly takes place through a REST API, which passes queries and submissions to a main server handling job scheduling and job result retrieval. A separate module shall be responsible for executing the jobs. Once this architecture is set up, the following step would be to containerize the different components of the system and utilize contemporary container orchestration tools, such that it is possible to deploy the platform in some cluster. However, the platform shall still be usable locally without the need for any containerization and orchestration, to maximize community access.

In addition, a non-functional requirement of the project is to apply Python's style guide [PEP 8](#), as well as static type analysis and unit testing of the existing codebase. This would facilitate a more sustainable open-source environment, and would increase trust in the platform's code.

To sum up, this project concerns itself with rethinking the architecture of ABAQUS, and not extending the list of its features. The final deliverable shall again be a proof-of-concept prototype, that can be improved upon in further iterations in the future.

ABSTRACT

The recent increased interest in quantum computing has led to the release of many of open-source quantum frameworks by commercial vendors and researchers alike. The implementation details of each framework could result in very different performances when executing some quantum routine, and thus it is important to be aware of the relative performance advantage a framework may have over the other, such that the proper tool is chosen before undergoing a new project or research. The Automated Benchmarking of Algorithms for Quantum Systems (ABAQUS) project targets this exact issue as part of Quantum Technology Initiative (QTI) at CERN, and a prototype has been developed last year.

While the developed prototype served well as a proof-of-concept, it had two main issues. First, it was not intuitively extensible. One of the goals of ABAQUS is for it to be community-driven, and therefore, the design had to be more intuitive, especially to people coming from non-CS backgrounds. Secondly, the underlying low-level design was not scalable, which does not fit with the Distributed Quantum Computing paradigm, that is also part of the QTI.

Accordingly, the prototype has been modified, getting closer to both goals, by making the different components more modular, and adapting the system such that it can be scaled with the use of container technologies and container orchestration tools. This makes the prototype usable in different configurations: locally, in a virtualized environment, or a distributed cluster.

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1 Introduction

The quantum hype is real, and one of the very obvious evidences of that is the amount of open-source quantum frameworks we have right now (a non-exhaustive list can be found [here](#)). This of course poses a decision-making challenge and raises the barrier of entry for the non-experienced user, or even to experts who simply did not have the opportunity to experiment with the different quantum frameworks, either due to administrative or logistical reasons. Thus, the idea for the Automated Benchmarking of Algorithms for Quantum Systems (ABAQUS) was born. The main goal of the initiative is to create a platform where it is easy to run the same quantum routine on different quantum frameworks, providing relevant metrics that shall aid the users in deciding the framework(s) they should use for their projects.

The main philosophy of ABAQUS is for it to be community-driven, with its usage paradigm ranging from simple beginner-friendly local experimentation, to advanced large-scale cluster-based deployment, with more control over the computational resources, for more precise benchmarking results. As far as the former usage paradigm is concerned, work has already been done in the previous development iteration. However, the developed architecture was not suitable for a cluster-based environment.

In this project, we have modified the existing architecture of the platform and extended it such that the aforementioned philosophy is realized more closely. This was done by abstracting away benchmarking requirements as separate jobs that are executed by independent worker processes, which store the results in a database. Python is still the main programming language. For technologies, we are still using [Flask](#) for serving our application, in addition to [redis](#) and [RQ](#) for the job queuing and execution. For our database, we are using [MongoDB](#). And finally, we are using [Docker](#) and [Kubernetes](#) for the containerization and orchestration of the application, respectively, with [Prometheus](#) as the main monitoring tool. In addition, unit tests have been written and style guides and types have been enforced, using each of [pytest](#), [black](#), and [mypy](#), respectively.

The rest of the report would be as follows: [Section 2](#) would describe the high-level design of the system. [Section 3](#) includes the API specifications, with an explanation of the server endpoints and the Job ID generation methodology. After that, the JSON schema that we expect the users to follow when submitting their benchmarking requirements is summarized in [Section 4](#). [Section 5](#) would describe the Worker (the main execution component of our system) and its logic. [Section 6](#) would describe how the system is containerized and how it interfaces with Kubernetes to automatically scale on demand. Finally, [Section 7](#) would include closing remarks and ideas for future development iterations.

2 High-level System Design

2.1 Clarification of the Terminology

Before we get into the details of the design of our system, some terminology must be clarified first:

- A **quantum backend** refers to real quantum hardware or numerical simulators that are able to execute quantum commands. It should be noted that each configuration of some quantum backend that would result in different low-level behaviour is considered a *separate* quantum backend.
- A **benchmarking task** is a predefined quantum routine or a manually defined list of

Figure 1: Components of the System

steps that would result in some expected quantum behavior. An example of a predefined routine is the Quantum Fourier Transform (QFT).

- A user submits a **benchmarking configuration**. This is a JSON that contains information about the desired **benchmarking tasks** and the **quantum backends** that the user would like to run them on.
- Out of this configuration, one or more **benchmarking jobs** are created, depending on the different combination of parameters present in the configuration. More on this in [Section 4](#).

2.2 The System Components

The components of the system, as well as the high-level main flow of interactions that occurs between them and the technology used, are illustrated in figure 1, and are as follows:

- A Job Queue is used to store the job configurations until their execution. For this matter, the [Redis-Queue \(RQ\)](#) package is used, which abstracts away a lot of the complexities of having to deal directly with [redis](#), a popular in-memory caching framework that offers high flexibility and is usually also used as a job queuing service.

- Apart from abstracting away a queue data structure, RQ also provides means for specifying how the enqueued jobs shall be executed, and allows callbacks to be passed down to the queue in case of job success or failure. In RQ terminology, this is known as a worker, which is a system process that listens on the queue in redis and starts executing jobs as they come in the manner they were specified, and reporting back the status of the execution to RQ. There can be several instances of the worker, since the jobs can be independent and can all be executed in separate processes. While preparing for the execution of a job, the worker would load the required quantum backend from the Frameworks Pool, which is not an actual entity of the system, but is helpful when visualizing the job execution routine.
- For long-term storage of the results of execution, a [MongoDB](#) instance is used for storing the results as documents in a NoSQL database. Although much simpler, and more lightweight database engines could have been used, such as [TinyDB](#), handling the presence of multiple workers would have introduced the need for concurrency control on the data source. MongoDB takes care of this natively.
- For serving the application to clients, which would typically be an independently developed front-end, a Flask server is used. This server's main services, which are triggered through a RESTful API, are:
 - Receiving specifications of the benchmarking tasks that need to be carried out, enqueueing them in a queue, and returning back information that would be useful for retrieving information on the created jobs later on.
 - Receiving queries regarding the jobs in the system. For this service, the server interacts with both the job queue and the database. This is due to the fact that some of the user's jobs may still not be processed, and thus would still be in the queue, while finished jobs (whether successfully or not), would be available in the database.
 - Providing information about the possible benchmarks that can be carried out by the system. This is particularly useful for the frontend, which can ask the server for this information, and accordingly adapt the view to the user, by only displaying the only benchmarking options supported. This reduces the maintenance needed on the frontend when the Frameworks Pool grows or when more quantum routines are supported.

Two other components of our system, that are only relevant when running the system in a virtualized environment as well as a cluster, are:

- [Prometheus](#), which takes care of monitoring the system. Current implementation of the system only provides information regarding the number of jobs still waiting in the queue. However, it is very easy to add more metrics for monitoring in future.
- [Kubernetes](#), which is responsible for the orchestration of the different components of the system, and controlling the incoming traffic to the server, as well automatically scaling the number of the workers, either up or down, based on the number of jobs in the queue; a value that is tracked and monitored by Prometheus.

3 API Specifications

In this section, the API would be explained in more detail, listing the different endpoints that are available to the client, and differentiating between functional endpoints and development-related ones. In addition, the job ID generation methodology and how it relates to querying the jobs on the system would be described.

3.1 Endpoints

A typical RESTful API would offer endpoints representing the four main CRUD (Create, Read, Update, Delete) operations. However, given the nature of our system, some restrictions, clarified in the table below, are imposed to ensure a smoother run of the system. In addition, we provide no endpoint for updating submitted jobs. A user would have to delete the now-undesired job and re-submit it with the modified configuration. All of the current endpoints, with the exception of those relating to development purposes, are prefixed with `/api/v1`, reinforcing the API semantic. Tables 1 and 2 below list the endpoints for developers and clients, respectively.

Endpoint Suffix	HTTP Method	Behavior
<code>/</code>	<code>GET</code>	This endpoint does nothing but always return a <code>200</code> response with a JSON containing text that confirms the server is up and responsive.
<code>/metrics</code>	<code>GET</code>	This endpoint is mainly used for monitoring the system, and follows the format expected by Prometheus when reading the metrics of a system. Currently, it returns a single-line string denoting the number of jobs currently in the queue, but additional lines can be added in the future if more metrics are required.
<code>/rq-dashboard</code>	Implementation-Specific	This is a non-native part of the system that provides a monitoring UI for the queue, providing information on the workers and failed jobs. More information can be found in the public GitHub repository of <code>rq-dashboard</code> : https://github.com/Parallels/rq-dashboard

Table 1: System Developer Endpoints

3.2 Job ID Generation and Querying

When a configuration is submitted, the server first generates a unique ID that would prefix the ID of all the jobs that would be generated from this configuration. This is done using Python’s `UUID` module, where version 4 of the UUID protocol is used. Then, after the jobs has been generated, an ID is generated for each in the following manner: the identifier of the

Endpoint Suffix	HTTP Method	Behavior
/benchmarking_options	GET	This endpoint returns a JSON comprising the different benchmarking options that are expected to be received by the server. The options include the quantum backends supported, the options for building benchmarking tasks, and the types of output that can be requested from the quantum backends.
/submit_configuration	POST	This endpoint accepts benchmarking configurations from users in the form of JSON files, with the different fields providing the information required to run the benchmarks. Upon receiving the HTTP request, the server would validate the contents of the file against the schema available, before enqueueing the benchmarking jobs in the Job Queue. On success, the server sends back a 200 response with a JSON containing the configuration's unique ID, and the IDs of the jobs submitted to be used later for asking for results.
/get_jobs/<id_query>	GET	This endpoints queries both the Job Queue and the Database using the id_query present in the route, retrieving both pending and finished jobs, and sends back a JSON with information about the pending jobs' position in the queue, and the results of running the finished jobs. In case no jobs corresponding to the ID query were found, a 404 response would be sent back to the user.
/cancel_jobs/<id_query>	DELETE	This endpoint, similar to the previous one, queries both the queue and the database for jobs using the query, and goes on to remove all the jobs that are in the Job Queue, returning a 200 response with a JSON containing the IDs of the jobs removed. If the jobs found were only in the Database (which would denote that they are already executed and therefore can not be canceled), or no jobs at all were found with the query, a 404 response is returned with the corresponding information.

Table 2: System Client Endpoints

backend and its specification are joined by an identifier of the task to be run with a colon. The mapping from a task’s details to an ID is summarized in table 3 below.

Benchmarking Task	Expected Parameters	ID Pattern
Quantum Fourier Transform	Number of Qubits	<code>QFT-<number_of_qubits></code>
Random Circuit	Number of Qubits, randomization seed, circuit depth	<code>Random-<seed>-<depth></code>
Manual Task	List of quantum steps	<code>Manual-<steps_hash></code>

Note: The hash of the steps is computed by simply appending the string representation of all the steps and then using the BLAKE function to hash the resulting string into an 8-byte hash of which the hexadecimal representation is used for the ID

Table 3: Mapping of a Task to an ID

With that said, any job on the system would be identified by an ID of the following pattern:

`<Configuration’s Unique ID>:<Quantum Backend’s ID>:<Task’s ID>`

When a user attempts to retrieve information about jobs or cancel a job that they submitted, it is expected that they would use one of the formats in table 4 for carrying the desired operation in a single batch, otherwise their query would be rejected by the server.

Format	Expected Result
<code><Configuration ID></code>	All jobs with such a configuration ID
<code><Configuration ID>:<Backend ID></code>	All jobs that has this configuration ID and were run on the quantum backend with the given backend ID
<code><Configuration ID>:<Task ID></code>	All jobs that has configuration ID and task ID equal to the passed parameters
<code><Configuration ID>:<Backend ID>:<Task ID></code>	All jobs that has configuration ID, backend ID, and task ID corresponding to the passed parameters. Typically, this should return at most one job.

Table 4: ID Query’s Possible Formats

3.3 An Example Sequence Diagram

We close this section with a sequence diagram summarizing a lot of the information that has been clarified. Figure 2 illustrates the typical manner a user would be interacting with the system, starting with the very first request made for submitting a configuration, until requesting the result and getting a response back.

4 Benchmarking Configuration JSON Schema

As mentioned before, the server receives the benchmarking configuration in the form of a JSON object. To ensure that the requested benchmarks are valid, the object is validated against a JSON schema that specifies the expected keys and values in every configuration. Below we summarize the schema, starting with the three main keys each JSON object must have:

Figure 2: A Typical Sequence of Events in the System

- **backends**: an array of `quantum_backends` objects, that must contain at least one item. A `quantum_backend` object has the following schema:
 - **framework**: this is the name of the core quantum framework to use. Currently, this is only allowed to be from the list [`qiskit`, `pennylane`]. This list has to be manually extended by developers once they integrate with additional frameworks.
 - **backend_type**: the type of backend to be used from the provided quantum framework. Right now, and since we only support simulators, the user has the option to choose one from [`pure_state`, `mixed_state`], depending on whether they would like to incorporate noise into their benchmark. However, in future iterations, a more exhaustive list of options can be present to the user, where for example they would have the option to decide the quantum device they wish to run their algorithm on. In addition, the available options can be different depending on the core framework chosen.
 - **is_gpu_supported**: This is a simple boolean flag that determines the users wish to use the GPU for executing the benchmark. Again, the schema should be adapted in the future once the platform is adapted for real quantum hardware, where this flag should be ignored.
 - **kwargs**: a key-value mapping for potential extra arguments that might be needed when instantiating the backend. An example of this would be the number of OMP threads that the qiskit simulator is allowed to use using the `max_parallel_threads` parameter.
- **backend_hyperparameters**

- **output_type**: one of the values in the list [`statevector`, `density_matrix`, `expectation_value`, `measurements`] denoting an output typically available in quantum simulators. It should be noted that further validation has to be added in the future since [`statevector`, `density_matrix`] can not be retrieved from real hardware.
 - **kwargs**: a key-value mapping containing potential extra arguments for the function retrieving the output. An example of this would be the number of shots to use if the `measurements` value is chosen.
- **benchmarking_tasks**: an array of `benchmarking_tasks` objects, that must also contain at least one item. A `benchmarking_task` follows the following schema:
- **task_type**: the type of benchmarking task to run. Right now, the user can choose from [`Manual`, `QFT`, `Random`].
 - **n_qubits**: the number of qubits to run the benchmark on. This is only required for tasks where this value can not be deduced, which means it is ignored for the `Manual` task.
 - **steps_list**: an array of `steps` objects. This again has to be of a non-zero size. A `step` object is an array of fixed size 3 (semantically equivalent to a triple) where the elements, in order, are expected to be:
 1. A string representing the quantum operation to apply. Right now, this can be one of [`X`, `Y`, `Z`, `CNOT`, `CZ`, `CY`, `RX`, `RY`, `RZ`]
 2. An array of minimum size 1 and maximum size 2, representing the qubits to apply the operation on. A uniqueness requirement is applied on the elements. It should be noted that the maximum size would have to be changed in the future when operations affecting more qubits are considered.
 3. An arbitrary JSON object that is supposed to represent a key-value map containing any additional parameters for the quantum operation. Currently, this is only expected to hold the parameter of the parameterized gates [`RX`, `RY`, `RZ`].
 - **save_output**: a boolean flag denoting whether the user would prefer the output of the benchmark to be stored and returned to the user. This item is boundless. However, in a networked setting, we recommend restricting this possibility only up to a reasonable of qubits in case the user is requesting the statevector or the density matrix, to avoid network congestion.
 - **kwargs**: a key-value mapping similar to above. This object can be used to pass information to the `Random` task, such as the random seed to use, or the maximum depth of circuit to generate. However, if the user provides no such information, the defaults on the server would be used instead.

A benchmarking configuration following the above schema would be used to generate a number of jobs equal to the total number of quantum backends multiplied by that of benchmarking tasks. In other words, a configuration hypergrid is generated from the given variables. An alternative would have been having each quantum backend contain a list of benchmarking tasks that the user would like to run on this specific backend. Similarly, benchmarking tasks can each include the list of quantum backends to be run on. Each variation has its pros and cons, and none can serve as a silver bullet. In the future, a meta-schema can be defined that would allow for more flexibility where a user can generate the configuration dynamically given the options provided by this meta-schema.

5 The Worker Module

As described, the worker is the main execution component of the system, that consumes jobs from the queue as they come, by preparing the benchmarking environment and then running the benchmarking task. Sometimes, it may be necessary to run the task several times, taking the average value of the benchmarking metric and the standard deviation, to eliminate any execution ‘noise’ that may influence a reading of the metric.

The main returned object of the execution routine is a Python dictionary that would include information relating to the computational resources that were used (this is currently implemented very roughly and should be refined in the future), the job configuration mirrored back, and the benchmarking results as well as the returned output of the quantum backend, if requested.

Callback Functions Apart from the main execution function, there are two additional routines present in the module that get called by the Redis-Queue library depending on the status of the execution. In the case of success, extra information regarding the job ID and the status of execution would be added to the dictionary before the final dictionary is stored as a document in the database. Otherwise, in the case of failure, the traceback string, that is captured by Redis-Queue, would be added to the dictionary for the user’s reference. In case the job configuration or the resources data were not present in the dictionary due to the interruption caused by the failure, they would be added here as well. Finally, the job ID and the status are included as before before the document is stored in the database.

Stand-alone Manually-Triggered Benchmarks Although so far the worker has only been described as a component in a larger system, the implementation of the execution function allows for it to be used in a stand-alone manner, where the user can simply just import it from the `worker` module and pass the desired job configuration. In this scenario, the post-processing functions described would not have any effect, since they are only accessible in a Redis-Queue context.

The Low-level Implementation The execution of a benchmark takes place in several stages. First of all, the backend is instantiated using the passed quantum backend parameters. These are used to dynamically load the backend’s class from the `backends` module as long as they used the naming convention that is common among all the implemented backends. For example, in the current implementation, the class names of all backends end with the suffix `Backend`, and the prefix, which is expected to be the actual name of the framework, is capitalized, so the class name of qiskit’s backends would be `QiskitBackend`. This makes the system much easier to extend, as the developer will not have to determine the required backend through a cascade of `if-else`, but rather would only need to create a class with a name following the convention. Each backend class is expected to inherit from the `QuantumBackend` class, which requires each child to implement a `backend` and a `run_task` functions. The latter is the function invoked by the execution function to run the benchmarking task once, storing any resulting readings or metrics in the backend’s instance. Those readings are then accessed by the function after running the task the required number of repetitions with the desired aggregation.

6 Containerization and Autoscaling with Kubernetes

With the new architecture, users have the option to run the system in many different configurations, with varying levels of complexity and control over the hardware resources. We already mentioned the ‘manual’ method where a user would import the execution functions from the `worker` module and then go on to use it to run benchmarks. Another option would be to manually run each of the different components of the system, where the user would first instantiate the redis and MongoDB servers as processes on their machine, and then start the worker as well as the API server.

To leverage the architecture, where we have a proper separation-of-concerns, and each component’s objective is semantically close to its name, we can make use of containerization technologies. Such technologies offer a more lightweight, agile virtualization of services, with an easier control over the available resources of the system. For our purposes, this is most important when we try to increase the credibility of our benchmarks by minimizing interference from other system processes that might deplete our benchmarking process of necessary resources, causing a prolonged execution period. This may be an undesired consequence if we are comparing the execution speed of different simulators, for example. Therefore, containerization may benefit users who demand resource-critical benchmarks and would prefer having such a ‘promise’ of resource availability throughout the whole duration of the benchmarking experiment.

6.1 Building the Docker Image

We include a `Docker` image of our platform in the GitHub repository. Two challenges had to be tackled when creating the image. The first was incorporating the `rq-dashboard` library. Due to flawed maintenance of the public repository of the package on GitHub, the most up-to-date version is not actually on the default branch, but rather a different one. Therefore, manual cloning of the repository and reset to the required commit had to be done, before carrying out the installation steps. Of course, this issue is of no concern to whomever does not really require this dashboard, but we include it by default, and leave the modification to the specific developer’s needs. Another issue was the size of the image. Using a typical single-stage build script, the image got as big as almost 1.8GB. Even though this might not be considered a lot in comparison to an average Docker image, it was deemed a lot given how we expect some user to prefer having several instances of the worker component to consume jobs more quickly. Therefore, we attempted reducing the size of the image using multi-stage builds, where we first build the Python wheels of all the dependencies of our package in the main Python base image, before copying only those wheels to the slimmer Python base image and installing them there. This technique has reduced the size of the image to about 800MB; a decrease of about 1GB of data. The size of the image can be reduced further by not including the quantum frameworks as dependencies of the package, and rather acquiring them on the fly, by importing them from some volume. This is only an idea for the future, and we satisfy ourselves with the current image size. Our script automatically starts the API server once the installation is over.

6.2 Starting the Platform with Docker Compose

As mentioned before, we need to instantiate both redis and MongoDB for our service to fully function. This is easily done by writing down a `docker-compose` file where we list the Docker images of both services, and properly bind them to the built platform image. For the database to function, though, we must also set up a persistent volume, or otherwise the data

would be lost every time the container is deleted. For monitoring the API server, we include a [Prometheus](#) service in the Compose file to monitor the number of jobs still in the queue as we described in the API Specifications section.

The configuration of the worker service can be more involved, since now it is possible to reserve computational resources for the container or specify a limit for the resources it is allowed to use, using the [resources](#) keyword in the configuration YAML file. The worker service uses the server's image as well, but uses a different command since we do not wish to start another API server in the container. Instead, we run a command from Redis-Queue's CLI that starts listening to any changes that happen to the queue on the Redis server.

Using Compose makes it very seamless to manually deploy extra replicas of any of the services we specify, and so system administrators can dispatch extra instances of the worker service if they so wish, as well as provide it with extra computational resources.

6.3 Deploying in Kubernetes Clusters

So far, the paradigm used to start the application should be sufficient for the majority of users, who are expected to run small- to medium-scale benchmarks, and do not require real-time adaptation of the resources to increasing demand, and would rather just manually modify whatever needs to be modified as the need arises. However, for serving a large team of scientists/experimentalists continuously running benchmarks as part of their experiments, it may be a better option to go bigger and deploy the platform on a cluster, where the services are managed in a more automated manner. For this reason, we include a minimal example of deploying the platform on a Kubernetes cluster in the GitHub repository, and automatically scaling the number of worker instances horizontally. In this part, we summarize the steps that run sequentially to have the system fully deployed.

6.3.1 Deploying the Main Components

For development purposes, we first start by creating a local cluster using [minikube](#), a simple tool for starting a Kubernetes cluster locally. Once the cluster is up and running, we first create a [PersistentVolume](#) for the database, followed by a [PersistentVolumeClaim](#) for reserving this volume for use by the database. We then go on to create the [Deployment](#) and the [Service](#) artifacts for both of the redis and MongoDB services. For those unfamiliar with Kubernetes, it should be noted that the [Deployment](#) manifest is responsible for creating [Pods](#) running the specified containers, while the [Service](#) manifest specifies the [Pod](#) ports that should be exposed either within the Cluster or to external processes as well.

After that, we build the image described in the last section inside [minikube](#)'s environment, such that it is available for use by the Kubernetes Engine. With this, we carry out the same deployment steps for the API Server. However, the server still can not be accessed from outside the cluster, which is why an [Ingress](#) object must be created, to specify the routes that may be allowed into the cluster. The [ingress](#) add-on must, however, be first activated inside [minikube](#). In this scenario, we only allow routes prefixed with [/api/v1](#) and [/rq-dashboard](#).

Finally, we deploy the worker. We do not require a [Service](#) object here, since we do not need to expose any ports of the worker container, as it only needs to pull jobs from redis.

6.3.2 Activating Automatic Scaling

At this point, the system would be working exactly as it has before. Now we go on to summarize the steps needed for automatically scaling the worker instances.

First, we set up the [Prometheus operator](#), which is simply an extension to Kubernetes for running Prometheus instances. A lot of the Kubernetes jargon would be omitted here since it is irrelevant to the main logic. The only thing to note here is that the operator is set up such that it would read existing metrics in the services in the cluster by attempting to access the [/metrics](#) route. Services are only monitored if a [ServiceMonitor](#) object associated with the service to be monitored is created. This object declares the service to the Prometheus instance, and specifies conditions that must be met to monitor the service, as well as configures the metric scraping procedure, such as the port to use, and the interval between each scrape. As mentioned, this route exists on the API Server and returns the number of jobs in the queue.

Once the Prometheus deployment is able to read the metrics from our server, we are supposed to integrate it with the Custom Metrics API of Kubernetes. This would allow Kubernetes to later on use the value of this metric however we please. So, we set up an [adapter](#) for Prometheus, declaring the metric that we would like the Custom Metrics API of Kubernetes to read from Prometheus, which in our example deployment is called [queued_job_count](#).

The last step is the simplest of the above. We only need to create an instance of the [HorizontalPodAutoscaler](#) artifact, that would listen to the metric we just declared to Kubernetes, and accordingly adapt the number of replicas of the worker. In the specification, we tell Kubernetes to only look at the final value in the time-series of the metric's value history. We also tell Kubernetes to only listen to the metric if its value is coming from the API server service, in case other services are reporting a metric of a similar name. We also specify the minimum and maximum number of replicas of workers Kubernetes is allowed to dispatch.

After all of the aforementioned steps, one should have a fully-functioning deployed instance of our platform, with user access only limited to the specified ports and routes, that also automatically adapts to increased load by instantiating extra worker instances, and then falling back to a smaller number once the load is processed.

7 Conclusion and Outlook

We have completely re-designed ABAQUS to make it more scalable and flexible. With the minor re-design of the interface with the quantum frameworks, we allow the users to have more control over how they would like benchmarking tasks to run on specific quantum backends, by giving them more breathing space between instantiating the backend and running the actual benchmark. And through the use of containers, we allow users of the system to control the amount of computational resources they want to make available, which would result in more reliable benchmarks given a unified hardware configuration present to all the benchmarking jobs. We also provide an example of how the platform can be deployed to a Kubernetes cluster. We also increased the quality of the GitHub repository by incorporating unit tests for the different components of the system, adding type hints to all functions to enable static type analysis, and applying Python's PEP 8 style guide.

The job is far from done, and there is more that can be done to make ABAQUS more favorable to the community. Some ideas and suggestions were already mentioned in the text of this report. We summarize some of those points again and mention some additional ones:

- **Interfacing with real hardware:** Since the current implementation only includes interfaces with quantum simulators, it would be a reasonable next step to interface with some real quantum hardware. This is highly likely to demand several architectural decisions from future developers, who are going to have to find a sensible way for managing API keys for accessing the quantum machines; a typical authorization technique used by commercial vendors. Apart from the actual interfacing with real hardware, the developers

would also have to come up with metrics for comparing between different hardware that are very likely going to be based on different physical phenomena.

- **More frameworks:** Right now, interfaces with only two frameworks are present, which is not sufficient for stress-testing the platform and retrieving some benchmarking metrics that can be contrasted with some of the publicly-available benchmarking data. Therefore, it is recommended to integrate with at least two more frameworks. The more ambitious future developers may decide to even attempt interfacing with non-Python-based quantum frameworks, such as [Yao.jl](#).
- **Support for multi-version benchmarks:** With the current implementation, only the latest version of each framework would be used for running the tasks. It is possible that users would like to benchmark different versions of the same framework, to decide whether they should pump up the version they are currently using or not, for example. This may require tweaking of the default directory structure that is used by [pip](#) when installing packages.
- **More Benchmarking Tasks:** For reasons similar to those above, more benchmarking tasks should be added to the platform to make it more impactful. One such task could be one of the many variational algorithms that are heavily studied right now, such as VQE, QAOA, or QNNs. Of course, such addition would impact the worker algorithm and the schema radically, since it would require an incorporation of the classical part of those algorithms, which largely consists of the optimizer that modifies the weights and parameters of the quantum gates.
- **Better Configuration Schema:** The current schema, although very effective, is still lacking. For example, it has no way of properly configuring noise models. In addition, the current processing of the configuration may not reflect how typical users of the system would prefer to use it. As mentioned in the text, there are variations for how benchmarking jobs can be constructed from the schema, and the current algorithm may have to be adapted to be more flexible and accept several of those variations.

In closing, we would like to appreciate what a very interesting area quantum computing is, one that is bringing together people from so many different disciplines, inspiring all of them to learn from fields which sometimes can be very diametrically opposed to their own. We hope that our platform be one of the catalysts that enable and promote the momentum of this learning process and collaboration spirit.

